

Exploring the Drivers of Employee Retention: The Roles of Organizational Support, Work-Life Balance, and Empowerment in Job Satisfaction

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The study primarily investigates the roadmap for employee retention by assessing the impacts of indirect variables of organizational support, work-life balance, and employee empowerment on job satisfaction. By this analysis through structural equation modeling, the researcher investigates the other variables like salary, diversity and inclusion, flexibility in working, stress level, and future career opportunities, analyzing the relative impact on job satisfaction. It also correlates organizational working culture, workplace diversity, and work-life balance, which strongly improve satisfaction. At the same time, job stress and misalignments in employee empowerment will detract from the satisfaction. This study covers the importance of positive practices to boost employee satisfaction and suggests balanced empowerment practices to avoid unintentional job stress. These valuable insights will provide practical contributions for HR managers and top management to design tailor-made retention strategies for employee satisfaction.

Keywords: job satisfaction, employee empowerment, structural equation modeling, job stress, retention

The basic challenge for today's Industrial Management is employee retention. The employee turnover rates become so high that they negatively impact organizational performance financially as well as nonfinancial. Various experts have laid down the study in the past that give insight the significant impact of employee retention on job satisfaction. Various studies have noted the significant impact of job satisfaction on employee retention. It suggests that employees who have more values about their job remain long lasting with the organization (Naz, 2020). This study mainly targets indirect factors like organizational support, work-life balance, employee empowerment, etc., impact on job satisfaction and employee retention. By analyzing specific corporate practices, this research study will provide practical information for managing a positive

work environment that boosts job satisfaction and employee retention (Amadi & Ndubueze, 2016)

The factors like a conducive workplace environment, flexi working, and honest working efforts contribute to the high level of job satisfaction and make the employees feel more attached and objective to the organization (Sanchez-Hernandez, 2019). In addition to this, flexi working timings and work-life balance generate high retention rates as employees are in a position to maintain a balance between their personal life and professional life (Bahar, 2022). Though after considering the noticeable impact of these findings, some other factors show more contradictory impacts on job satisfaction. Ex. Employee Empowerment and job engagements generally leads to motivating employees, but sometimes, if not properly managed, they create stress, which may negatively affect job satisfaction (Cyriac & Baskaran, 2020).

The purpose of this study is to identify and measure the impact of various factors on job satisfaction and to determine how these, in turn, affect employee retention. Using quantitative analysis, including path analysis and structural equation modeling, we examine ten factors hypothesized to influence job satisfaction, including compensation, diversity and inclusion, job stress, organizational culture, and person-organization fit (P-O Fit). Additionally, this research investigates the extent to which job satisfaction mediates the relationship between these factors and retention. The study contributes to the broader conversation on employee retention by offering a nuanced understanding of the indirect and direct influences on job satisfaction, with practical implications for human resources management and organizational leadership.

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Review of Literature

The literature on employee retention suggests that job satisfaction acts as a central mediator through which various organizational factors influence employees' decisions to stay or leave. Herzberg's

Two-Factor Theory, which divides job satisfaction determinants into 'motivators' and 'hygiene factors,' provides a foundational understanding of how certain workplace elements drive employee satisfaction (Frye et al., 2020). While motivators, such as personal growth and achievement, directly boost satisfaction, hygiene factors like compensation and job security, though necessary, may not increase satisfaction beyond a certain threshold (Azami et al., 2023). Studies focusing on millennials and Generation Z employees underscore the growing importance of factors like work-life balance and meaningful engagement in ensuring high satisfaction and retention (Islam et al., 2024).

Organizational support has been frequently highlighted as a key driver of employee satisfaction and retention. According to Ruiz (2017) a supportive work environment fosters loyalty and reduces turnover, especially when employees perceive that their organization values their well-being. Similar findings are reported in studies on work-life balance, where flexible work arrangements have been shown to significantly enhance job satisfaction (Sánchez-Hernández, 2019). On the other hand, high levels of job stress can erode satisfaction, making it imperative for organizations to implement stress management and wellness programs (Fei et al., 2024).

Empowerment and engagement initiatives are generally viewed positively, as they allow employees to exercise autonomy and participate in decision-making processes. In some research studies, empowerment leads to double-edged effects. On one side, it improves job satisfaction through promotion and work freedom, while on the other side, if not managed properly, it may lead to an increased workload and additional stress, which leads to job dissatisfaction (Cyril & Baskaran, 2020).

Person-organization Fit (P-O Fit) is also a very significant parameter of job satisfaction. The study clarifies that co-alliance between employee preferences, values, and organizations' working culture contributes to improving employee morale and work engagement (Hassan et al., 2021).

The above literature clarifies a multivariable approach to employee retention, which suggests that management of the organization should carefully balance the positive practices like flexi working and employee expectations to enhance job satisfaction, leading to reducing labor turnover.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the effects of various organizational factors on job satisfaction.
- To explore the relationship between job satisfaction and employee retention.

Research Questions

- How do the factors - organizational support, employee empowerment, and work-life balance impact employee job satisfaction in the workplace?
- What are the factors related to job satisfaction that have a significant impact on Employee retention?

Hypotheses of the Study

This research study is based on a set of null hypotheses. Each null hypothesis stressed that studying the individual factor has no significant impact on job satisfaction. Such factors include Wage, salary compensation, workplace diversity, employee job engagement, empowerment, Flexi timings, work stress and well-being, career growth opportunities, work culture, Person-organization fit (P-O Fit), performance appraisal, and skill mapping. The prime hypothesis is the

significant and positive impacts of job satisfaction on employee retention. By testing hypotheses, we will come to know the factors that significantly impact job satisfaction, which leads to employee retention.

Hypothesis of the Study

“Null Hypotheses (Each factor's influence on the Individual):

- *H0*: Compensation, Perks, and Leaves has no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Diversity and Inclusion have no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Employee Engagement and Empowerment has no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Flexi Working Hours and Work-Life Balance has no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Job Stress and Employee Well-Being have no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Learning and Career Opportunities have no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Organization Culture and Climate has no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Person-Organization Fit (P-O Fit) has no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Performance Appraisal has no effect on Job Satisfaction.
- *H0*: Skill (Competency) Mapping has no effect on Job Satisfaction.

Method

This research study undertakes path analysis through Structural Equation Modeling SEM and a quantitative research design to investigate the impact of various organizational factors on employee job satisfaction and retention. The use of SEM is to examine the complex relationship between various variables to study their direct and indirect impacts on employee job satisfaction and retention.

Measure and Analysis

This research study employs required statistical tools to investigate the strong and significant relationship between various variables. Path coefficients measure the way in which each factor impacts job satisfaction. A t-test was employed to determine statistical significance; at the same time, p-values determine the acceptance or rejection of the null hypotheses related to each factor. For the Implementation of each factor, from the survey, specific parameters were used to enumerate abstract concepts, such as compensation was measured through employee responses for salary, wages, and leave policy; workforce diversity was measured through inclusivity; Flexi timings were measured through schedule flexibility and work-life balance approach in the organization. The other factors, like work culture, stress level, career growth opportunities, P-O Fit, employee wellbeing, Performance appraisal, and skill mapping, were worked out to ensure consistent measurement.

This research methodology provides in detailed assessment of various factors that impact job satisfaction and provides a strong conceptual model for understanding how job satisfaction impacts employee retention.

Data Collection

The data collection was completed through a structured survey of employees across various industries for generalization. The survey includes demographic profiles like age, gender, experience, employment level, industry nature, which provides a diversified

range of different prospects on job satisfaction and employee retention. For the Structured Equation Model SEM analysis, sufficient samples were taken to get statistically significant results. The survey participants respond to the various factors like wage and

salary compensation, work-life balance, employee empowerment practices, work culture, and stress management practices within the organization.

Data Analysis

Figure 1
Employee Retention Structural Model with Performance-Driven Job Satisfaction Focus

Table 1*Path Coefficients of Direct Effects (Final Results)*

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	p	Hypothesis Decision
Compensation_Perks and Leaves -> Job_Satisfaction	0.004	0.007	0.056	0.07	0.944	Rejected/ Not Rejected
Diversity and _Inclusion -> Job_Satisfaction	0.501	0.498	0.123	4.062	0	
Employee _Engagement and _Empowerment -> Job_Satisfaction	-0.338	-0.335	0.111	3.047	0.002	
Flexi Working_Hours and Work_Life Balance -> Job_Satisfaction	0.463	0.451	0.122	3.789	0	
Job Stress _and Employee_Well Being -> Job_Satisfaction	0.892	0.882	0.201	4.431	0	
Job_Satisfaction -> Employee_Retention	0.48	0.485	0.039	12.464	0	
Learning and_Career Opportunities -> Job_Satisfaction	-0.181	-0.169	0.093	1.934	0.053	
Organization_Culture and _Climate -> Job_Satisfaction	0.166	0.164	0.058	2.884	0.004	
P-O Fit -> Job_Satisfaction	-0.259	-0.254	0.108	2.408	0.016	
Performance_Appraisal -> Job_Satisfaction	-0.137	-0.131	0.051	2.657	0.008	
Skill (Competency)_Mapping -> Job_Satisfaction	-0.299	-0.297	0.116	2.585	0.01"	

The null hypotheses suggest that not all the factors may have a significant effect on job satisfaction. The results in Table 1 detail each factor's influence, using Path Coefficients to indicate the strength and direction of relationships, along with t-test analysis and p-values to assess significance.

Compensation, Perks, and Leaves

Path Coefficient: 0.004, t: 0.07, p-value: 0.944

Hypothesis Decision: Not Rejected

Explanation: The data suggest that compensation, perks, and leaves have no significant effect on job satisfaction, as indicated by the very low path coefficient and a high P value (0.944). This finding implies that, in this context, job satisfaction may be driven more by factors beyond financial or material compensation, such as work environment or support systems.

Diversity and Inclusion

Path Coefficient: 0.501, t: 4.062, p: 0.000

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected

Explanation: Workplace diversity and inclusion have a strong and positive impact on employee job satisfaction. It has been remarked through the high path coefficient-0.501 and a significant p value of -0.000. It states that employees who have participated in diversified workplace environments report higher job satisfaction. The commitment of the organization to inclusivity boosts the sense of attachment, which significantly enhances employee job satisfaction.

Employee Engagement and Empowerment

Path Coefficient: -0.338, t: 3.047, p: 0.002

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected

Explanation: Interestingly, the negative path coefficient (-0.338) indicates that employee engagement and empowerment have an inverse relationship with job satisfaction in this context. This unexpected result could suggest that while empowerment is intended to boost morale, it may also introduce pressures or expectations that negatively impact satisfaction. This finding could point to a need for balanced empowerment initiatives that support autonomy without

creating additional stress.

Flexi Working Hours and Work-Life Balance

Path Coefficient: 0.463, t: 3.789, p: 0.000

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected

Explanation: Flexibility in working hours and a good work-life balance have a significant positive effect on job satisfaction, as shown by a high path coefficient (0.463) and a p value of 0.000. This suggests that when employees are offered flexible schedules that support their personal lives, they are more likely to feel satisfied with their jobs. Work-life balance appears essential to creating a fulfilling work environment.

Job Stress and Employee Well-being

Path Coefficient: 0.892, t: 4.431, p: 0.000

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected

Explanation: Job stress and well-being play a substantial role in job satisfaction, as shown by the high path coefficient (0.892) and significant p-value (0.000). Low stress levels and strong well-being measures contribute greatly to employees' satisfaction, suggesting that well-being programs or stress reduction initiatives are critical. Organizations focusing on reducing job stress are likely to see increased job satisfaction.

Job Satisfaction and Employee Retention

Path Coefficient: 0.48, Mean: 0.485, Standard Deviation: 0.039, t: 12.464, p: 0.000

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected (indicating a significant relationship)

Explanation: The analysis reveals a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee retention. The path coefficient of 0.48 suggests that job satisfaction is a substantial predictor of an employee's likelihood to stay with an organization. This result is supported by the high T statistic (12.464), indicating a high level of confidence in the relationship's validity. Additionally, the very low P value (0.000) confirms that this effect is statistically significant.

Learning and Career Opportunities

Path Coefficient: -0.181, t: 1.934, p-value: 0.053

Hypothesis Decision: Not Rejected

Explanation: Learning and career opportunities show a weak, negative impact on job satisfaction, with a path coefficient of -0.181 and a borderline P value (0.053). This result could imply that while career growth is important, in this context, it may sometimes lead to stress or high expectations that dampen job satisfaction. Alternatively, it could suggest a perception that growth opportunities are limited or insufficiently supported.

Organizational Culture and Climate

Path Coefficient: 0.166, t: 2.884, p-value: 0.004

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected

Explanation: Organizational culture and climate have a positive impact on job satisfaction, with a path coefficient of 0.166 and a significant P value (0.004). This indicates that a supportive and cohesive workplace culture contributes to employees feeling more satisfied. Positive organizational values and a supportive climate likely make employees feel valued, enhancing their overall satisfaction.

Person-Organization Fit (P-O Fit)

Path Coefficient: -0.259, t: 2.408, p-value: 0.016

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected

Explanation: Person-Organization Fit shows a negative impact on job satisfaction, with a path coefficient of -0.259 and a significant p-value (0.016). This negative relationship may suggest that misalignment between employees' values and the organization's culture reduces job satisfaction. The findings indicate that when employees feel less aligned with the organization, they may experience lower satisfaction, pointing to the importance of cultural alignment.

Performance Appraisal

Path Coefficient: -0.137, t: 2.657, p-value: 0.008

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected

Explanation: The impact of p-value on performance appraisal has a significant but negative impact on employee job satisfaction. The p pathway coefficient of -0.137 and p value 0.008 clarifies dissatisfaction with appraisal methods and or outcomes. It may be due to perceived fairness or effectiveness of approaches. It may improve through a transparent and constructive feedback mechanism that influences employee job satisfaction.

Skill (Competency) Mapping

Path Coefficient: -0.299, t: 2.585, p-value: 0.010

Hypothesis Decision: Rejected

Explanation: The impact of skill mapping is negative on employee job satisfaction. The path coefficient of -0.299, and the p-value is 0.010. It shows that while valuable competency mapping may generate stress on employee performance expectations. So, it negatively impacts employee job satisfaction. To improve this relationship, it requires a supportive and growth-oriented competency assessment, and not one that creates stress.

The above analysis reflects that Flexi timings, Work force diversity and Inclusion, Work stress, well-being, and culture of

organization have significant positive impacts on employee job satisfaction, confirming its importance. In contrast with this, Employee Engagement, Person-Organization P-O Fit, and performance appraisal have negative impacts w.r.t. increasing work pressure and lead to reduced employee job satisfaction if not considered properly. In this way, we can say that a positive work environment, motivating policy structure, and balancing expectations from employees boost employee job satisfaction.

Discussion

This finding reflects an integrated relationship between various organizational factors and employee job satisfaction. Likewise, the factors work diversity and inclusion, flexi timings, and work culture in the organization have a positive impact on employee job satisfaction. In the case of work diversity and inclusion, there is a positive impact shown by the path coefficient = 0.501, =0.000, which indicates that such inclusive practices at the workplace enhance higher job satisfaction. Flexi timings and balance work life also have a positive impact on employee job satisfaction. In addition to this study, the importance of employee needs (Basha et al., 2022) also plays a very important role. Surprisingly, this study finds negative path coefficients for factors like employee engagement and empowerment, P-O Fit, and performance appraisal. In the study, there are negative path coefficients for employee empowerment, -0.338, which reflects that employee empowerment may improve results but also convert into work stress and lead to reduced satisfaction (Cyriac & Baskaran, 2020). There is also a negative impact of performance appraisal, leading to a reduction in satisfaction, -0.137. There is a need for equality and fairness, transparency, and a constructive feedback mechanism in the organization. This study also reveals that employee job satisfaction is a significant factor for employee retention, path coefficient of 0.48, reflecting a high positive relationship. So, it is clear that satisfied employees would like to stay long with the organization, considering job satisfaction is a critical element for retention.

Conclusion

This study concludes that job satisfaction is influenced by various supportive factors like inclusive policies, employee empowerment practices, etc., in an integrated manner. The factors like work diversity and work-life balance have positive impacts on employee job satisfaction, but at the same time, work stress and misalignment in person-organization fit can detract from it. The findings also highlight that organization that wants to improve employee retention should focus on inclusiveness, work-life balance with stress management, and care requirements while working on employee empowerment that should not convert into unwanted pressure. Further research could also be extended on this study by exploring industry-specific practices and assessing the impacts of these factors across various demographics on employees. So, by targeting this many areas, organizations can create a stronger and supportive workplace environment that contributes to employee satisfaction and ultimately achieves high retention.

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